

**"IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING THE
SUBJECT" HISTORY OF UZBEKISTAN " IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF
SOCIALLY ACTIVE CIVIC COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS"**

TESHAYEV AZIZBEK TOYNOR OG'LI

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences

Abstract: One of the prerequisites in the world is the creation of socially active civil competence, which is important to increase human capital (Human Capital)² in the development of the abilities of young people of the 21st century to actively participate in scientific research in the "Data science"¹ Direction. Particular attention is paid to the fact that the social activism of each citizen in the requirements set out in the Copenhagen Council's document 3 on the criteria of humanity is an indicator that determines the progress of society. In this regard, the formation of leadership qualities in young people, their upbringing as a socially active person, through an excellent study of the history of the motherland, national spirituality, is gaining special relevance.

Keywords: axiological, acmeological, development of socially, environmental and information, pedagogical, communication technologies

Introduction:

Scientific research is being carried out on the implementation of programs that assess unique abilities in the personality of a CIVIC-socially active citizen in the educational system of developed countries of the world, including the United States, Japan, France, Russia, Germany, Singapore, England, in their research on improving educational efficiency. Developing socially active civic competence in young people in a Global educational environment, "...creation of a creative-innovative developing environment in teaching, leadership in education, content of creative, socio-personal qualities..."⁴, the need to apply technologies based on the integration of World educational programs in the education of active personnel who will succeed in the future, ensure the development of society.

In our country, "in harmony with the implementation of the concept of the new Uzbekistan - enlightened society, the formation of legal knowledge and culture in their minds by giving priority to the study of the history of the country to young people, teaching rich history, scientific and cultural heritage, national-religious values of our people "youth - The" reforms" to ensure the realization of the idea of the third renaissance under the slogan "the builders of new Uzbekistan" ...the country

is setting the task of 5"to train a high new generation of specialists with intellectual and spiritual potential, who are able to take the field and implement them with new initiatives and ideas for combing". In this sense"...the formation of a strong immunity against various ideological threats, in particular religious extremism, terrorism and other foreign ideas, is one of our main tasks by increasing youth activity in reforms to build a Democratic state and develop civil society, expanding the ranks of enterprising, ambitious youth, raising the culture of the use of youth legal, environmental and information and communication technologies”

Compliance of the study with the priorities of the development of Republican Science and technology. Dissertation research Republican Science and technology development I. "In the social, legal, economic, cultural, cultural, cultural and educational development of an informed society and a Democratic state, the formation of a system of innovative ideas and ways of their implementation" was carried out within the framework of the priority direction.

The degree of study of the problem. Issues of formation of social, spiritual activity in a person on the scale of our republic and education of the Civil position Q.Quranbayev, O.Musurmunova, M.Makhmudova, H.Tojiboyeva, I.Ergashev, A.Jumayev, G.Tulenova, I.Safarbuyayeva, G'.Pirnazarov, H.Khamzayev, S.The problems of improving the form, method and technologies of the formation of competencies in students are reflected in the research work of akkulovas.Asadov, N.Turdiyev, M.Vakhobov, R.Ishmuhamedov, N.Gurbanov, Y.Najmiddinova, K.Umataliyeva, A.Khodjabayev, U.It was analyzed in the research work of the mingboevs.

The purpose of the study is to improve the methodology of teaching the subject "history of Uzbekistan" in the development of socially active civic competence of students.

Objectives of the study:

Clarification of the importance of the content of socially active civil competence of students in the process of studying the subject” history of Uzbekistan " on the basis of prioritization of pedagogical and psychological opportunities and didactic principles;

improving the criteria for assessing the level of development of students by teaching socially active civil competence “history of Uzbekistan” on the basis of Project technology;

improving the model of teaching the subject "history of Uzbekistan" on the basis of innovative technologies aimed at improving socially active civil competence in students;

improving scientific and methodological recommendations on improving the effectiveness of teaching the subject “history of Uzbekistan” based on axiological, acmeological approaches in the development of socially active civil competence of students in the process of Higher Education.

The object of the study is the process of teaching the subject “history of Uzbekistan” in the development of socially active civil competence of students of higher educational institutions.

The subject of the study is the content, tools, forms and methods of developing socially active civil competence of students in the process of Higher Education.

Methods of research. When conducting research work, methods of comparative-critical study and analysis of political, philosophical, sociological, psychological, pedagogical literature on the problem; study of regulatory legal documents and literature on education; study of advanced pedagogical experiments in higher educational institutions, analysis and synthesis, Social Survey, sociometric methods, mathematical-statistical analysis of the results of a pedagogical experiment were used.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study on improving the methodology of teaching the subject "history of Uzbekistan" in the development of socially active civil competence of students, the following conclusions were drawn:

The relevance and social significance of the development of socially active civil competence in students is established in the concept of educational development until 2030 as one of the important tasks to contribute to the development of society in ensuring the stability of a democratic society, achieve results such as economic development, the rise of legal culture, social justice and equality, solving global problems,

References:

1. Teshayev A.T. Akmeologik yondashuv asosida bo‘lajak tarix fani o‘qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirish //Pedagogik mahorat - Buxoro, 2024. №3. – B.161-165. (13 00 00 №23)
2. Teshayev A.T. Akmeologik yondashuv asosida «O‘zbekiston tarixi» fanini o‘qitish metodikasini takomillashtirish orqali talabalarning ijtimoiy faol fuqarolik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish modeli //Pedagogika jurnali 2024, 5-son, B. 33-36. (13 00 00 №6)
3. Teshayev A.T. “O‘zbekiston tarixi” fanini o‘qitish metodikasi mazmunini talabalarda faol fuqarolik kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish asosida takomillashtirish

// Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali Impact Factor: 8.2 | 2181-3035 | № 14(51) B. 63-71. (13 00 00 №39)

4. Teshayev A.T. Talabalarning ijtimoiy faol fuqarolik kompetentligini rivojlantirishga oid ilmiy tadqiqotlar tahlili //“Pedagogik akmeologiya” xalqaro ilmiy-metodik jurnali. 4(12)2024. B.161-165. (13 00 00 №38)